

PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR DEVELOPING ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILLS IN STUDENTS BASED ON LEARNING OUTCOMES

A.E. Narbayev

National Center for Knowledge and Innovation in Agriculture, Director of Samarkand Region

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17518580>

Abstract. *The article provides general information on the state of entrepreneurship education and aims to identify potential gaps in the knowledge and skills of graduates of vocational technical schools and colleges, in relation to labor market requirements. The main goal is to "develop scientific and innovative approaches and entrepreneurial skills for students by creating conditions for graduates to find employment in Central Asia."*

Keywords: *market economy in vocational education, entrepreneurship, student, entrepreneurial skills, scientific and innovative approaches, component, criterion, level, competence.*

Introduction

In February 2023-2024, 7 vocational educational institutions (Engineering; Electric Power; Manufacturing and Processing Industries; Electronics; Electronic Equipment; Instrumentation; Energy and Radioelectronics; Service;) and the number of employees: 114, students, 1343 graduates, more than 617. First of all, it provides general information about current proposals for entrepreneurship in vocational education. The main goal should be to achieve the results of self-assessment in vocational educational institutions on "Training students for entrepreneurship" and "Preparing students for entrepreneurship and supporting them". Third, the results of the survey among employers and graduates are presented to identify potential mismatches in the skills requirements of the labor market and the skills of graduates in the area of entrepreneurship skills, which once again encourages the development of a targeted strategy for the sector. Fourth, a general discussion of the identified shortcomings and mismatches of skills is presented. In conclusion, these aspects allow for a comprehensive examination of the state of entrepreneurship education in vocational education. Finally, conclusions are drawn on the further development of entrepreneurship education in vocational schools, colleges, technical schools, and vocational schools in vocational education.

Entrepreneurship education seeks to equip students with the knowledge, skills and motivation to generate ideas for entrepreneurial activities in a variety of settings, both as individual entrepreneurs and as employees in established organizations, entrepreneurship is a key competence for all students that supports personal development, active citizenship, social inclusion and employability. Organizational change is needed because implementing the entrepreneurship and innovation agenda the potential depends on the management structures, organizational capacity, and institutional culture of educational institutions, as well as the characteristics of the surrounding economy.

After intensive reforms in the field of education in the past few years, professional educational institutions in Uzbekistan have gained more freedom to provide dual education. Small business and private entrepreneurship have been identified as priority areas of our country's

economy. Over the past seven years, about 3 thousand laws, decrees and resolutions have been adopted aimed at developing this sector. 115 licenses and permits for entrepreneurial activity were canceled, a notification procedure was introduced for 34 types of activities. The procedures for obtaining permits were simplified and the terms for their issuance were reduced by an average of 2 times. Unnecessary inspections were canceled, restrictions on the circulation of cash, currency, and raw materials were lifted. As a result of such opportunities, the number of new business entities is rapidly increasing, and the activities of existing ones are expanding. Over the past seven years, the number of entrepreneurs has increased almost fourfold. Many businessmen have expanded their businesses throughout the country, creating millions of jobs and becoming large, successful companies. A class of entrepreneurs with their own brands in the domestic and foreign markets has begun to form.

We also offer students the knowledge, skills and desire to support entrepreneurial success in a variety of situations. Entrepreneurship is an important component of the strategy of educational institutions. Entrepreneurship is now a key topic for students of all disciplines, aimed at developing entrepreneurial skills in students. In the words of our President, the time itself has begun to demand from us that we pay attention to the development of skills that will allow students of colleges, technical schools and vocational schools to realize their potential as future producers and employers.

The educational institution organizes business project and startup competitions and implements science-based entrepreneurship curricula in all areas of education. Mentoring students is necessary to develop entrepreneurial skills and competencies. The educational institution, together with external stakeholders, designs and implements a curriculum for teaching entrepreneurship. The organization regularly collaborates with stakeholders to better understand the demand for future skills. The organization takes the following measures:

- Develop and improve a new curriculum that guides students towards creative entrepreneurship and supports the process of practical training.
- Encourage students to participate in various business activities, such as business groups, courses, and competitions.
- Increase the number of informal entrepreneurship training courses and ensure that the college or technical school, if necessary, provides opportunities to acquire entrepreneurial skills and qualifications in the curriculum in preparation for a scientific and practical degree.
- Establishing various partnerships with local communities and organizations, local and regional governments, chambers of commerce, industry, and alumni will create a pedagogical foundation for developing entrepreneurial skills in students based on learning outcomes.

The adoption of the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On additional measures to attract young people to entrepreneurship and support their business initiatives”, and the fact that all “Business Fundamentals” teachers in the regions are being trained by specialists from Germany in order to ensure the implementation of this Resolution, are evidence of the serious attention our government is paying to this issue. At this point, it is important to be able to distinguish between the concepts of entrepreneurship and business:

Entrepreneurship (entrepreneurial activity, this is business) is an independent activity carried out on a risk-based basis, aimed at regularly obtaining income from owning property, selling goods, or providing services. Entrepreneurial activity (entrepreneurship) is an initiative activity carried out by business entities in accordance with the law, aimed at obtaining income (profit) at their own risk and under their own property responsibility.

Depending on the purpose, type and direction of entrepreneurial activity, it can be divided into production, commercial, financial and consulting types. And these, in turn, are divided into types.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, according to Article 5 of the Law on Entrepreneurship, there are the following forms of entrepreneurship:

- Individual entrepreneurship;
- Private entrepreneurship;
- Collective entrepreneurship;
- Mixed entrepreneurship.

In order to develop entrepreneurial skills in students, various meetings, master classes, and business trainings are held in our vocational school with large entrepreneurs and business owners.

Improving the economic training of future junior specialists is a very urgent issue, which is determined by the specifics of the market economy. Any professional must have a deep knowledge of the basics of the market economy and have good professional and economic skills. The creation, education and development of an "economic person" is becoming an important issue on the agenda, and the economic views of specialists working in various life situations and economic and network systems, regardless of their profession, are considered to be economic knowledge, a condition and basis for the personal and professional formation. It is no exaggeration to say that the human and civil status, economic situation, financial capabilities, lifestyle, economic thinking, and economic culture of an individual depend on their economic literacy.

Theoretical foundations of teaching entrepreneurship subjects are an integral part of the system of training senior specialists. This factor plays an important role in developing and improving the economic literacy of students of non-economic educational institutions, educating them as competent specialists, and improving their skills.

The relevance of the problem was proven by the experience gained during the study of economic knowledge and entrepreneurial skills with students from various colleges, the development of a new model for the development of economic literacy, and the development of criteria for assessing economic knowledge, skills, and competencies.

The study results showed that our hypothesis that all components of economic entrepreneurship skills should be carried out in a coherent and interconnected manner with vocational education in developing economic literacy in students is justified. According to the results of the study, the pedagogical foundations of the formation of entrepreneurial skills in students. The main goal of research on entrepreneurial skills is to form and implement a connection between entrepreneurial pedagogy, entrepreneurial intention, and the ability of students to identify and use new opportunities and new innovations in current vocational education in the entrepreneurial process.

The results of the study suggest that students' worldview and interest are key tools in developing entrepreneurial skills. This study sheds light on the subtler effects of entrepreneurship programs on students' learning and entrepreneurial processes by highlighting the heterogeneous nature of entrepreneurship pedagogy. This implies that the recognition and effective use of these opportunities depend on the asymmetry of knowledge and learning that results from the asymmetry of entrepreneurship pedagogy. My conclusion is that the relationship between theoretical and applied pedagogy is reciprocal in producing effective learning outcomes, requiring integration in teaching practice. This is an important factor in developing entrepreneurial skills in students.

The emergence of entrepreneurship as an academic discipline over the past three decades has coincided with the global proliferation of entrepreneurship education programs in vocational education. It is based on the clear premise that it can stimulate students' entrepreneurial attitudes and intentions, skills and competencies, and the ability to adapt startup projects and implement new innovations.

It refers to the methods and approaches adopted by teachers to implement methods to facilitate the teaching of entrepreneurial skills in students. Teaching approaches are based on different philosophical natures and are based on different educational theories and content, which can lead to specific individual learning outcomes and depth of learning. Therefore, the effective outcome and effectiveness of learning outcomes depend on the pedagogical techniques and content used. A recent stream of literature compares how the impact of different pedagogies changes, including the organization of dual education in vocational education students in the formation of entrepreneurial thinking self-efficacy is also a key step towards entrepreneurship.

This study is a starting point for understanding how entrepreneurial skills formation in students shapes the entrepreneurial process in emerging students. Based on the analysis and discussion of this article, I conclude that the different learning experiences we have received from different entrepreneurship pedagogies have led to knowledge asymmetries and differences in entrepreneurial competencies, thus emphasizing the discovery and exploitation of opportunities. I encourage future researchers to expand this line of research and continue to explore pedagogical approaches, learning processes, and the mechanism of opportunity identification and exploitation; entrepreneurship educators can combine theoretical and experiential teaching methods to provide potential students with a broad range of competencies and up-to-date knowledge of the entrepreneurial process.

REFERENCES

1. Khizrich R., Peters M. 'Predprinimatelstvo ili kak zavesti sobtvennoe delo i dobitya uspekha - Moscow: Progress-Unevers, 1991. - 160 p.
2. Muradova N.S. Predprinimatelstvom ne rojdayutsya // Obrazovanie i obshchestvo. – 2003. – No. 4. - S. 56 - 58. 5. Hayek F.A. background. Competition and open procedure // Mirovaya ekonomika i mejdunarodnye otnosheniya. – 1989. – No. 12. – P. 6 – 14.
3. People's word 2023 (A. Salimov), -2.
4. R. Rikhsiyeva 2024 Introduction of dual and entrepreneurship in education - 14-21.